

PROCEDIN

Building Procurement Capability for Embedding and Driving Innovation

D1.1

Procurement of Innovation

Buyers Resource Base

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PROCEDIN

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List of Abbreviations and Acronyms

CA	Consortium Agreement
CE	Circular Economy
CPV	Common Procurement Vocabulary
EIC	European Innovation Council
EAFIP	European Assistance for Innovation Procurement
GA	Grant Agreement
GM	Green Mobility
EISMEA	European Innovation Council and SMEs Executive Agency
POI	Procurement of Innovation
WP	Work Package

1 Summary

This deliverable, D1.1, aims to address the challenges faced by buyers in effectively participating in procurement opportunities.¹ Buyers often lack the necessary resources and face capacity building issues. This document provides a **comprehensive mapping of resources, best practices, and successful case studies for buyers**. Additionally, it takes a comparative approach to explore the variations in procurement opportunities across different regions in Europe, identifying areas where the process is streamlined and highlighting regions where challenges persist.

The deliverable focuses on **understanding and overcoming barriers and obstacles encountered by buyers** during the procurement process including contract management. By examining both sides of the equation, including the perspective buyers, it offers valuable insights into the dynamics of procurement and presents strategies to equip buyers with the necessary tools to navigate these complexities. Collaboration and synergy-building with other resources involved in the procurement ecosystem play a crucial role in providing buyers with comprehensive support.

The key components of this task include:

1. **Mapping of Resources:** The deliverable provides a simple inventory of resources available to buyers, such as training programmes, funding opportunities, and advisory services, which assist them in procurement process and contract monitoring. By consolidating this information, buyers gain access to a centralised resource base, simplifying their efforts in finding relevant support.
2. **Best Practices and Success Stories:** Successful case studies of frontrunners in the field of procurement are highlighted. By examining these inspiring examples, other buyers can learn from their experiences, identify effective strategies, and replicate their success stories and best practices. This section serves as an inspiration and source of practical guidance for buyers seeking to improve their procurement capacity building.
3. **Comparative Analysis:** The deliverable conducts a comparative analysis of different regions within Europe, examining the varying degrees of streamlining in procurement processes. By identifying regions where procurement opportunities are more accessible and efficient, buyers can gain insights into successful models and potentially replicate them in their own regions. This analysis also sheds light on regions where challenges persist, highlighting areas that require attention and improvement.
4. **Overcoming Barriers and Obstacles:** Recognising the barriers faced by procurers alike, this deliverable offers strategies and recommendations for overcoming these challenges. It addresses issues such as limited resources, lack of capacity building, complex regulations, and lack of awareness. By understanding these obstacles and the solutions to tackle them, buyers can learn from it and improve their procurement processes.

By collaborating and building synergies with other stakeholders in the procurement ecosystem, this deliverable aims to **create a comprehensive resource base for buyers**. The [PROCEDIN Resource Bank](#), developed by the consortium partners, is set to become a **vital source of support and**

¹ Sections 1-3 of this report mirror the related deliverable D1.2. Whereas D1.1 addresses public sector buyers, D1.2 is aimed at small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). Both deliverables explain the PROCEDIN Resource Bank, the common survey which informed its design and related activities.

guidance for individuals and organisations interested in promoting circular economy and green mobility.

2 PROCEDIN Project Introduction

The adoption of procurement of innovation (POI) practices – which bring together business and sectors – relies on legal reforms, European, national and regional policies, growing expertise, guidance, tools and case studies, and networks of early adopters. However, to drive deep, systemic change, the rate, scale, and scope of POI adoption must increase.

To accelerate POI in the specific domains of **Circular Economy (CE) and Green Mobility (GM)**, in the context of European cities' innovation for sustainability and resilience agendas, this project will leverage existing resources and its members' pan-European professional networks, and initiate new provisions to enhance and mobilise POI motivation, knowledge, and skills.

The complex landscape of growing expertise, experience, and learning infrastructure will be mapped, and resources will be related to the varied needs of different stakeholder archetypes (defined by organisation type, extent of POI experience, etc.) to identify and address key gaps in provision. Special attention will be given to promoting enduring access to, and increased uptake of, POI guidance and learning resources for buyers and vendors, and building leadership capacity for driving and embedding innovation through strategic procurement.

2.1 PROCEDIN Project Objectives

Collectively, encouraging POI capability development and accelerating the growth of CE and GM innovation ecosystems are essential components to meet European Green Deal goals and priorities for societal resilience. The following **PROCEDIN's objectives** are carefully crafted with that in mind:

- 01.** To map, make more accessible, and promote the use of, POI development resources.
- 02.** To map and mobilise key POI stakeholders to accelerate and embed POI adoption.
- 03.** To develop, provide and promote uptake of guidance on legal frameworks.
- 04.** To facilitate procurement leadership in driving and embedding POI to generate dynamic innovation ecosystems.
- 05.** To disseminate project activities, resources and other outcomes throughout the duration of the project, via multiple channels to reach all stakeholder groups.

This deliverable with focus in more detail into all the activities that will support the **Objective 01**, as it aims to map, make more accessible, and promote the use of POI development resources.

This Deliverable has a core **link to deliverable D1.2**, and it is an integral part of the project, tightly linked to **Milestones 2, 3, and 4**.

3 Mapping of Resources

This report outlines the planning, design, and implementation of the survey conducted within PROCEDIN WP1. The purpose of the survey is to compile a comprehensive list of resources relevant to the project's objectives. The report describes the survey strategies, sampling strategies, survey tools,

and the subsequent analysis process. The aim is to ensure the availability of high-quality resources for the development of a robust resource base.

3.1 Resource Mapping Survey

Each resource survey begins with careful **planning and design**. A survey strategy was prepared during WP1 meetings, which included the aim, method, sources/respondents, and quality criteria. The aim clearly defined the objectives and boundaries of the survey. The method outlined the step-by-step process, considering potential risks and barriers that may affect the quality of the process or findings. Mitigation measures are implemented to address these risks.

Additionally, a **sampling strategy** was designed to articulate the rationale behind the survey. This strategy identified target respondents, starting at the organisational level and then narrowing down to named individuals wherever possible.

The **survey instrument** was prepared by UT (Figure 1), which served as the tool for data collection. To ensure the plan's robustness, the draft plan was reviewed by other consortium members.

Figure 1. Resource Mapping Survey Main Page

The **Resource Mapping Survey** is being conducted using Qualtrics², an online platform to facilitate ease of distribution, response monitoring, and compliance with GDPR regulations. The surveys are actively monitored to expedite responses and ensure timely data collection. Upon receiving responses, they are promptly checked for accuracy, and any queries or clarifications are addressed as necessary in collaboration with the respondents.

The survey served as a pivotal **data collection mechanism for both D1.1 and D1.2**, facilitating the centralisation of information and data collected **from both private and** entities (Figure 2). The **scope of resources** sought encompasses various categories essential to project's objectives. These resources include:

- **Trainings & Training Materials:**
 - Comprehensive training programmes and accompanying materials that equip stakeholders with the necessary knowledge and skills in relevant procurement practices.

² <https://www.qualtrics.com/>

- **Capability and Skills Frameworks:**
 - Frameworks that outline the essential capabilities and skills required for successful procurement processes, enabling stakeholders to assess and enhance their capacities accordingly.
- **Consultancy Reports and European Projects' Outputs:**
 - Insightful reports generated by reputable consultancies, as well as outputs from European Commission-funded projects related to procurement, offering valuable analysis, recommendations, and lessons learned.

In addition to the aforementioned resources, project partners also solicited the provision of supplementary materials pertaining to the following areas:

- **Best Practices & Case Studies:**
 - Exemplary case studies and best practices showcasing successful procurement endeavours, enabling stakeholders to draw inspiration and replicate effective strategies.
- **Legal Frameworks:**
 - Documentation encompassing relevant legal frameworks, regulations, and guidelines governing procurement processes, ensuring compliance and fostering transparency.
- **Tools, Impact Assessments, and Other Resources:**
 - Practical tools, impact assessment methodologies, and other pertinent resources that aid stakeholders in optimising their procurement practices, streamlining processes, and achieving desired outcomes.

Figure 2. Resource Mapping Survey: Divider Page

As part of the survey, participants were presented with specific questions related to the **type of sector organisation** they represent. These questions aimed to gather valuable information about the nature and characteristics of the organisations.

Participants were given the opportunity to provide a self-description of their organisation, allowing them to elaborate on their unique characteristics and activities. An open-ended field was provided to enable participants to provide a comprehensive description.

These survey questions (Figure 3) provided insights into the diverse range of sector organisations participating in the survey, allowing for a better understanding of their profiles and roles within the procurement ecosystem.

UNIVERSITY OF TWENTE.

English ▾

Type of public organisation (*)

- Public Authority, Contracting Authority/Entity at EU level
- Public Authority, Contracting Authority/Entity at national level
- Public Authority, Contracting Authority/Entity at regional level
- Public Authority, Contracting Authority/Entity at local level
- Knowledge institute (association, university, NGO etc.)
- Other, namely:

What kind of organisation are you? How do you describe yourself?

Figure 3. Resource Mapping Survey: Type of Organisation

Within the survey, respondents were asked to indicate **their role within their respective organisations**. This question (Figure 4) aimed to gather information about the specific position and responsibilities held by the participants.

Your role within the public organisation (*)

- Procurer / Buyer
- Legal expert
- Decision Maker / Budget holder
- Policy maker
- Trainer / Teacher
- Technical expert (Advisor on specific topic, such as sustainability etc.). Expert on:
- Other, namely:

Figure 4. Resource Mapping Survey: Role within the Organisation

By capturing this data, the survey sought to gain insights into the diverse range of roles and responsibilities represented by the respondents. This information contributes to a comprehensive understanding of the participants' perspectives and expertise within the context of procurement processes and decision-making within their organizations.

Furthermore (Figure 5), respondents were asked to **classify the products or services** they manage within their organisation. This question allowed for the selection of multiple answers to capture the diverse range of offerings. In continuation, participants were requested to indicate **the country in which their organisation is located**. This question aimed to provide an overview of the geographical distribution of the survey respondents, enabling an understanding of the diverse regional contexts and potential variations in procurement practices across different countries.

English

Can you name potential relevant training, course or workshop providers in relation to public procurement? (add links if possible)

Do you have examples of Small and Medium Sized Companies (SMEs) or service/products/construction suppliers that managed the public procurement / tendering process particularly well and might be willing to be interviewed to help us capture best practice?

Figure 5. Resource Mapping Survey: Questions on Training, Resources and Buyers Examples

Respondents were encouraged to **identify any training, course, or workshop** providers that they perceive as relevant within the realm of procurement. This question aimed to uncover potential sources of expertise and educational resources that could benefit stakeholders seeking to enhance their understanding and skills in this domain.

In the following questions, participants were asked to **share any knowledge they had about resources** specifically designed to assist buyers in procurement processes. This question aimed to gather insights into existing support mechanisms that could be beneficial for buyers.

By posing these questions, the survey aimed to tap into the collective knowledge and experiences of the participants, enabling the project to identify relevant training providers, compile a comprehensive list of resources for buyers, and potentially engage with exemplary buyers as valuable sources for best practices.

The survey concluded with two questions (Figure) that aimed to gather insights from the participants regarding the **main enablers and barriers** associated with two specific aspects of procurement: procurement of innovation and responsible/sustainable procurement.

Enablers/Barriers

In your opinion, what are the top 5 main enablers and barriers of public procurement of innovation?

In your opinion, what are top 5 main enablers and barriers of responsible/sustainable procurement?

This survey has been funded by the European Union via the [PROCEDIN](#) project and the [URBAN AGENDA](#) network. Funded by the European Union

Figure 6. Resource Mapping Survey: Enablers and Barriers

The gathered information will contribute to a better understanding of the challenges and opportunities associated with procurement of innovation and responsible/sustainable procurement, thus informing the development of strategies and recommendations to address these factors effectively.

3.2 PROCEDIN Resource Bank

The **PROCEDIN Resource Bank** (Figure 7) developed by the consortium partners, is a **result of the Resource Mapping Survey**, and it is set to become a **vital source of support and guidance** for individuals and organisations interested in promoting circular economy and green mobility.

The partners acknowledge the plethora of development resources already available, such as training materials, best practices, and case studies. However, they also recognise that the resource landscape is complex and fragmented, making access to these resources challenging.

Therefore, the Resource Bank provides a **centralised hub of relevant and high-quality resources**, making it easier for learners to find what they need. In addition, the consortium partners aim to **promote successful innovation procurement** related to circular economy and green mobility, which is crucial in achieving the Green Deal and ensuring societal resilience.

Figure 7. PROCEDIN Resource Bank: Landing Page

The Resource Bank page on the project's website (Figure 8) has been designed to reflect the categorisation of resources into two distinct categories: **Resources for Buyers of Innovation** and **Resources for Suppliers of Innovation**. This strategic division aligns with the objectives outlined in Tasks T1.1 and T1.2, allowing users to easily navigate and access the specific resources that are most relevant to their roles and needs.

Figure 8. PROCEDIN Resource Bank: Resources Categorisation

The **Resources for Buyers of Innovation section** within the Resource Bank (Figure) is specifically designed to cater to the needs of both public and private buyers who are particularly interested in learn more about buying innovation and sustainable solutions.

By structuring the Resource Bank in this manner, the project website ensures that users can easily locate and access the resources most pertinent to their specific roles and objectives. It simplifies the search process and allows users to quickly find relevant information without sifting through unrelated materials.

Figure 9. PROCEDIN Resource Bank: Resources for Buyers Section

Additionally, the Resource Bank page emphasises the **importance of collaboration and knowledge exchange** between buyers and suppliers. It features filters that promote cross-category resources, encouraging buyers to explore supplier-related materials and suppliers to gain insights into buyer perspectives. This collaborative approach fosters a holistic understanding of the innovation procurement landscape and supports effective engagement between both parties.

3.2.1 Resource Bank Communication and Promotion Strategy

By implementing the following **communication and promotion strategy**, together with strategies elaborated within D5.1, the consortium aims for the resource bank to effectively reach its intended

audience, drive engagement, and establish itself as a valuable and trusted source of procurement-related resources.

- **Targeted Outreach:** Identify key stakeholders, including procurement professionals, and develop tailored communication materials to raise awareness about the Resource Bank. Utilise various channels such as email newsletters, social media platforms to reach the target audience effectively.
- **Engaging Content:** Develop engaging and informative content to highlight the value and benefits of the Resource Bank. This can include case studies, best practices, practical guides, and success stories that resonate with the target audience. Regularly update the resource bank with new and relevant content to keep users engaged and encourage return visits.
- **Collaborative Partnerships:** Establish collaborations and partnerships with other organisations and initiatives in the procurement field (e.g., Innovation Procurement Task Force). This can involve cross-promotion of resources, joint webinars or events, and sharing of expertise. Collaborative partnerships enhance the visibility and credibility of the resource bank, reaching a wider audience and fostering knowledge exchange.
- **Thought Leadership:** Position the Resource Bank and PROCEDIN as a thought leader in the procurement domain by publishing insightful articles, research papers, and thought pieces. Leverage the expertise within the project consortium to contribute to publications, participate in relevant conferences, and engage in panel discussions to showcase the resource bank's knowledge and value.
- **User Feedback and Testimonials:** Encourage users to provide feedback on their experience with the Resource Bank. Collect testimonials and success stories from SMEs and procurement professionals who have benefitted from the resources. Display these testimonials on the Resource Bank's website and in promotional materials to build trust and credibility among potential users.
- **Training and Workshops:** Organise training sessions and workshops to demonstrate the functionalities and benefits of the Resource Bank. These sessions can be conducted virtually or in-person, procurement departments, and relevant stakeholders. The training sessions should showcase practical examples of how the resource bank can be utilised to enhance procurement processes and outcomes.
- **Continuous Evaluation and Improvement:** Regularly evaluate the effectiveness of the communication and promotion strategy by monitoring website traffic, user engagement, and feedback. Incorporate user suggestions and feedback to continuously improve the resource bank and tailor the communication strategy to better meet the needs of the target audience.

PROCEDIN will also engage in broad communication through the network of the **Urban Agenda Partnership on Innovative and Responsible Procurement** and during the Urban Agenda Partnership meetings. By leveraging these networks, PROCEDIN can increase its visibility and reach within the relevant communities.

4 Analysis barriers and enablers

The analysis of the results from the survey on barriers and enablers are provided in a brief overview (Figure 10). The main barriers of buyers from PPI perspective were expertise, resources, behaviour in their organisations. The same barriers were mentioned by buyers from Responsible/Sustainable perspective. Regarding the enablers, the interaction with market, framework/rules/guidelines/criteria

where mentioned by the respondents for PPI. Next to framework/rules/guidelines/criteria was expertise mentioned by the respondents for Responsible/Sustainable procurement.

Figure 10. PROCEDIN Resource Bank: Buyers of Innovation – barriers and enablers

Understanding these barriers and obstacles is crucial in developing strategies and support mechanisms that address the specific challenges faced by buyers of innovation. Furthermore, the results are being used to shape priorities for WP3 and other facets of the agreement.

5 Conclusion and Next Steps

The Resource Survey conducted within PROCEDIN WP1 was an essential step in compiling a comprehensive Resource Bank, which is already live and accessible. Through careful planning, design, and implementation, the survey has gathered valuable resources relevant to the project's objectives. Nevertheless, the consortium will keep the Survey open to continue collecting relevant resources, and publish them within the project’s Resource Bank. Additional resources can also easily be suggested by users from within the website. Moreover, some of the next steps are the following:

- **Promoting Success Stories:** PROCEDIN will actively showcase success stories and relevant best practices. This will inspire and motivate other buyers to benefit from innovative procurement opportunities.
- **Resource Bank Development:** The resource base for both buyers and vendor firms will be further enriched with other relevant resources. This will provide buyers with comprehensive and practical tools to navigate the dynamics of procurement issues effectively.
- **Communication and Promotion:** Implement the strategy to raise awareness about the Resource Bank and its benefits, and leveraging existing platforms and networks to maximise the reach and impact of the Resource Bank.
- **Comparative Analysis and Knowledge Exchange:** Further comparative analysis will be conducted to deepen consortium's understanding of regional disparities in procurement of innovation.
- **Capacity Building and Training:** PROCEDIN will explore opportunities to provide capacity building and training programmes for buyers, equipping them with the necessary skills and knowledge to navigate the complexities of procurement processes effectively.
- **Monitoring and Evaluation:** Ongoing monitoring and evaluation will be conducted to assess the impact of PROCEDIN's interventions and initiatives. Feedback and insights from buyers and other stakeholders will inform the continuous improvement and refinement of the resource bank and associated support mechanisms.